

A STUDY OF THE FEASIBILITY OF SELF-CONCEPT AMONG THE ADOLESCENT SCHOOL STUDENTS IN PUSAD PANCHAYAT SAMITTEE

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ABSTRACT

Adolescent children are vulnerable to psychosocial stressors that are often under-recognized and under-treated. As a result, they can suffer massive losses and sometimes have limited access to the resources and support needed to mitigate the damage or deal with the consequences. Self-concept reflects how an adolescent evaluates himself or herself in the areas in which a student's achievement is important. This creates problems in front of the students and increases their difficulties and can lower their self-concept, sometimes even a low self-concept can create problems. During adolescence, students may have positive self-concepts in some areas and negative self-concepts in others. This research examines the level of self-concept among teenagers studying in private schools. 100 adolescent students from Pusad Panchayat Samiti of Yavatmal districts of West Vidarbha were selected for this research including 50 adolescent girls and 50 boys. A random sampling method was adopted for this. A descriptive survey method has been used for this research and the study was conducted regarding 100 adolescent students in the age group of 10-19 years from Pusad Panchayat Samiti in Yavatmal districts. A self-concept scale was used to collect data regarding this research. This research showed that self-concept plays an important role in adolescent students. Apart from this, this research reflects the need to develop these students by finding the factors that contribute to the development of the self-concept of these students.

KEYWORDS: *Self Concept, Adolescent students*

INTRODUCTION:

Adolescence is a period of rapid learning and developing sensitivity to affective acquisitions that determine the general style of adult life. Adolescents with high self-concepts achieve a high level of academic success, which will increase their recognition in society, better career opportunities, acceptance by peers, parents and teachers, and development. Leadership qualities and life skills will develop. As students move through adolescence, they face a variety of challenges, stresses, and opportunities. A key factor in dealing with these challenges is a positive self-concept. As students move through adolescence, schools should prepare them to become part of the general public with proper guidance. They can easily adapt to their surroundings. These students constantly struggle with

their self-concept and self-esteem, which leads to adjustment difficulties, drug abuse, depression, and even suicidal thoughts at times. As students transition from middle school to high school, their self-concepts gradually increase. The independence gained during this age gives adolescent children opportunities to engage in activities beyond what they are capable of. Able to receive support from others in socially acceptable ways. Self-concepts are positively related to academic performance but appear to be a consequence of performance rather than a cause of performance.

This shows that developing academic skills in students is a more effective means of developing their self-concept. Self-concept is defined as a person's values based on their characteristics, qualities, abilities, and actions. Self-concepts are not innate but are developed or created by the individual through interaction with the environment. Considering this interaction is an important aspect of self-concept because it suggests that these self-concepts can be modified or changed. A person's attitude towards himself is largely responsible for his success. An adolescent student who has adequate self-concepts can adopt a problem-solving approach and is spontaneous, creative, original and has high self-esteem. He believes in himself and is motivated to do well academically. Moreover, he is free to accept others without any negative feelings. Adolescents' negative self-concept is associated with a variety of maladaptive behaviours and emotional problems. Problems and difficulties in Haya can lead to low self-concept, But low self-concept can also cause problems and reduce motivation to study. Developing students' self-concept is one of the most important steps teachers and parents can take to build self-confidence in adolescents, ensuring a conducive environment for learning. There is a need to implement comprehensive education in schools that address not only academic but also personal and social competencies. Therefore, in this research, the self-concepts of teenagers have been studied.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Herrera, Al-Lal, and Mohamed (2020) analyzed academic achievement, as well as self-concept, personality, and emotional intelligence by participants' gender and cultural origin. In this, 407 students were selected for the research including 192 boys (47.2%) and 215 girls (52.8%), with an average age of 10.74 years. By cultural group, 142 students of European origin (34.9%) and 265 of Amaze origin (65.1%) were included. Their academic performance was evaluated based on grades obtained in three school subjects: Science, Language, Literature and Mathematics. The research revealed that language and literature grades can vary depending on the gender of the students. Similarly, gender differences were found in self-concept, personality and emotional intelligence. Also, physical self-concept varies by cultural group. Palomino (2017) analyzed self-concepts among students with learning needs to develop mindset-based psycho-educational. As such, mindfulness is a learning experience that includes significant emotional well-being, learning, and physical and mental health benefits for those engaged in the practice. The study was conducted at the primary school level. It showed that there was a positive correlation between peer relationships, physical appearance and physical ability and academic self-concept in mathematics.

Duraku and Hoxha (2010) studied the relationship between self-esteem, study skills, self-concept, social support, psychological distress, anxiety and academic performance in university and secondary-level students. It revealed that social support has a significant effect as a protective factor for anxiety. Poor study skills, self-concept, and psychological distress are items indicative of high levels of anxiety. It revealed that high levels of self-esteem are associated with high levels of student achievement.

Bharti and Sridevi (2015) studied self-concept in adolescents. Saraswati (1984) analyzed the self-concept of 40 adolescent students in the cities of Hyderabad, Telangana using the Self-Concept Scale. It revealed that a high percentage of adolescents had above-average levels of self-concept in temperament (85%), intellectual dimension (77.5%), physical (60%) and social (52.5%). About 47.5 per cent of adolescents had high and above-average academic self-concepts, and 57.5 per cent of adolescents had high moral self-concepts. Adolescents' overall self-concept was found to be 27.5 per cent high and 72.5 per cent above average. Therefore, this study is helpful for teachers and parents to maintain optimal levels of adolescent self-concepts.

Khan and Alam (2015) found in their study that there is a statistically significant negative relationship between academic stress and self-concept, academic stress and self-concept of government secondary-level students in Aligarh. Private school students were found to be significantly affected by moral self-concept and temperamental self-concept. One dimension of academic stress on private and government secondary-level students is the lack of a conducive learning environment in colleges. Kaur and Singh (2014), in their research on the self-concept of school students, found no difference between male and female students as well as between government and private schools. But a significant difference has been found based on the location of the schools of the school students. Students in rural areas have better self-concepts than urban schools. Students with three levels of self-concept, high, average, and low, differ from each other on all aspects of emotional intelligence. Students with high self-concepts are more emotionally intelligent than students with low self-concepts. Hence, a positive relationship was found between emotional intelligence and self-concept. Jain (2012) found in his study that low and high academic achievement groups did not show any significant difference for six areas of self-concept. It also showed that high achievers have positive attitudes toward school, teachers, and extracurricular activities, and that self-concept and academic performance are good predictors of general performance, establishing a relationship and prediction between self-concept and academic achievement. Ghazvini (2011) studied the relationship between academic self-concept and academic performance, in which he showed a close relationship between academic self-concept and academic performance. Academic self-concepts are powerful and positive predictors of general achievement in mathematics as well as literature. It asserts that adequate attention needs to be given to the development of self-concepts as well as the need to systematically guide teachers to work on this throughout the educational process. Tarquin et al. (2008) studied the relationship between students' prior experiences of alienation and various aspects of self-concept. Students were asked to report on their worst experience at school, the symptoms they felt after their worst experience, and their feelings about themselves. Results revealed a moderate negative correlation between self-concept and student disengagement.

THE OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

To study the feasibility of self-concept among adolescent school students in Pusad Panchayat Samiti.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This research has studied the level of self-concept among school adolescent children in Pusad Panchayat Samiti of Yavatmal districts of West Vidarbha. This study aimed to observe different aspects of self-concept in students' personal, family, social and adolescent life and to assess the extent of self-concept. A descriptive research method was used for this research. This research includes adolescent girls and boys studying in government and private schools. A total of 200 students have been selected for this research. A random sampling method was used for that. A standardized self-concept scale was used to collect data in this research. The scale consists of six factors

namely student behavior, anxiety, intellectual status, popularity, physical appearance and happiness and a total of 30 statements are determined. An inferential statistical technique has been used to analyze the facts obtained in this regard.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Table no. 1.1

Feasibility of self-concept among adolescent school students in Pusad Panchayat Committee

	Self-Concept	Low	Moderate	High
1	Anxiety	42%	22%	36%
2	Behaviour	24%	46%	30%
3	Stress	48%	28%	24%
4	Mental status	24%	52%	24%
5	Popularity	30%	42%	28%
6	Physical appearance	28%	42%	30%
7	Happiness	26%	46%	28%

A large number (36%) of the students in this research are in the age group of 15 years and 28% of the respondents are in the age group of 14 years. More than half of the respondents (54%) are women and 46 % are Majority of respondents (64%) have one sibling, 26 % of respondents have 2 siblings. The majority of respondents (74%) belong to nuclear families, and 26 % of respondents belong to the joint family system. The majority of respondents (88%) live with their parents, 8 %of whom are semi-orphans and 4 %are orphans. The majority of the respondents (64%) have their primary education in Marathi medium and 36% of respondents have English medium. The majority of the respondents (88%) reported that their family monthly income is between Rs. 15,001 to Rs. 30,000. We can understand from this study that more than half of the respondents have completed their education up to 10th standard out of which 48 %of the respondents have completed up to the high school level. The majority of the respondents (70%) do not have any health problems while 30 % of the respondents have health problems. It is also found that there is no significant relationship between years of living in a family and their self-concept. There is a significant relationship between respondents' interest in sport and self-concept. Participation of students in the sports field improves their self-concept There is no significant relationship between the health problems of the respondents; School challenges, respondent habits and self-concept. There is no significant difference between them. In terms of self-concept less than half of the respondents (46%) have a moderate level of self-concept, less than half of the respondents have a moderate level of self-concept regarding anxiety (42%), their behavior (48%) and physical appearance (46%), while Popularity (52%), happiness (42%) and intellectual status (42%) are the same. This shows that self-awareness needs to be developed in the student community and self-concept is important for improving the quality of life. In this case, they should focus on developing the self-concept of adolescent students to promote their mental health and personality. This study shows that the majority of rural students have a moderate level of self-concept and few have a low level of self-concept. Therefore, policymakers need to take the necessary steps to improve the level of self-concept among these students. Therefore, the human mind has an important relationship with human emotions, and the mind must give importance to self-concept to control its emotions. But their emotions need to be understood, taught, trained

and controlled by the mind. Self-concept goes beyond intelligence to a higher level of consciousness, guided by the senses, experience, and intuition.

Self-concepts are considered important in how an adolescent evaluates himself. Problems and difficulties faced by students can reduce their self-concept, But low self-concepts can also cause problems. Adolescence may have a positive self-concept in some areas and a negative self-concept in some factors.

The adequate emotional development of adolescent students to make proper use of their emotions to clarify the overall self-worth of the individual is the desirable need of the hour. The role of the social worker is to create awareness about self-concept and academic performance as well as psychological well-being in adolescents and its importance. Self-concept plays an important role in the field of research-oriented interventions for adolescent well-being in social work educational institutions. So it is necessary to implement social work methods at the school level to deal with various problems of school students.

CONCLUSION:

From this, it is clear that adolescents at the school level can evaluate their competence or abilities based on internal and external factors for the development of society. In India, many kinds of research have been done about general category students. In terms of self-concept. This research found that the majority of rural students have normal self-concepts and some students have low self-concepts. Policymakers and educational institutions in the social work sector need to take necessary steps in the area of research-oriented interventions for the well-being of adolescents at the school level.

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